

A Sieve Method for Proving Infinite Primes of the Form n^2+1

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Abstract

A sieve method with indication of the Chinese remainder theorem has been implemented to generate near square primes which are of the form $n^2 + 1$, where is n is a natural number. The resulting counting function which is the number of near square primes that are less than or equal to a larger natural number, N , is

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_{ns}(N) &\sim N^{1/2} \times (1-r_{p_1/p_1})(1-r_{p_2/p_2})(1-r_{p_3/p_3})(1-r_{p_4/p_4})\dots(1-r_{p_y/p_y})^{-1} + \Pi_{ns}(p_y) \\ &> 2C(p_y) \times N^{1/2}/[\ln(N)]^2 \end{aligned}$$

where $p_y^2 \sim N$, r_{p_x} , $x = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, y$, are the numbers of removed residue classes ($0 \pmod{p_x}$), and $C(p_y) = (1-1/2^2)(1-1/4^2)(1-1/6^2)\dots[1-1/(p_y-1)^2]$ is the twin prime constant according to the first Hardy-Littlewood conjecture. Thus, the conjecture of Landau's fourth problem that there are infinitely many near square primes of the form $n^2 + 1$ has been affirmed since $N^{1/2}/[\ln(N)]^2$ goes to infinity when N is infinitely large.

I. Introduction

Sieve methods with indication of the Chinese remainder theorem have become very powerful tools. It seems that several conjectures, such as Goldbach conjecture, twin prime conjecture, prime k -tuple conjecture, Alphonse de Polignac's conjecture, etc. have been affirmed with these methods.^[1,2]

In this paper, a sieve method with indication of the Chinese remainder theorem has been implemented to prove the conjecture of Landau's fourth problem that there are infinitely many near square primes of the form $n^2 + 1$, where is n is a natural number.

II. Sieve Method for Generating Primes $p = n^2 + 1$ and the Counting Function

For a set $S = \{n | n \text{ is a natural number, and } 1 \leq n \leq N\}$, and $N = p_1 p_2 p_3 p_4 \dots p_w$, where $2 = p_1 < p_2 < p_3 < p_4 < \dots < p_w$ are consecutive prime numbers, every number n in S has a unique residue vector with respect to moduli $(p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4, \dots, p_w)$ according to indication of the Chinese remainder theorem. There are total of $N = p_1 p_2 p_3 p_4 \dots p_w$ residue vectors. After removing n numbers that belong to r_{p_x} residue class of each prime number up to p_w , there are exactly $N_r = (p_1 - r_{p_1})(p_2 - r_{p_2})(p_3 - r_{p_3})(p_4 - r_{p_4}) \dots (p_w - r_{p_w})$ residue vectors left, representing the number of elements left from S . Thus, the ratio of the number of elements left to the original number of total elements in S is

$$N_r/N = (p_1 - r_{p_1})(p_2 - r_{p_2})(p_3 - r_{p_3})(p_4 - r_{p_4}) \dots (p_w - r_{p_w}) / (p_1 p_2 p_3 p_4 \dots p_w) \tag{1}$$

If \mathbf{N} is a multiple of $\mathbf{p}_1\mathbf{p}_2\mathbf{p}_3\mathbf{p}_4\dots\mathbf{p}_w$, the above equation is the exact ratio of \mathbf{N}_r/\mathbf{N} . Otherwise, it is an approximation.

The sieve method is to preclude the $\mathbf{n}^2 + 1$ values in the residue class $(0 \bmod \mathbf{p}_x)$ for all $\mathbf{p}_x^2 \leq \mathbf{N}$ from a set of natural numbers, $\mathbf{S}_n = \{\mathbf{n}^2 + 1 \mid \mathbf{n} \text{ is a natural number, and } 1 \leq \mathbf{n}^2 + 1 \leq \mathbf{N}\}$, where \mathbf{N} is a large natural number. The $\mathbf{n}^2 + 1$ values left after precluding are all near square primes since these values cannot be divided by all primes that are less or equal to $\mathbf{N}^{1/2}$. The original number of elements in \mathbf{S}_n is approximately equal to $\mathbf{N}^{1/2}$. Thus, the counting function which is the number of near square primes that are less than \mathbf{N} is^[1,2]

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{\Pi}_{ns}(\mathbf{N}) &\sim \mathbf{N}^{1/2} \times (\mathbf{p}_1 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_1})(\mathbf{p}_2 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_2})(\mathbf{p}_3 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_3})(\mathbf{p}_4 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_4}) \dots (\mathbf{p}_y - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_y}) / (\mathbf{p}_1\mathbf{p}_2\mathbf{p}_3\mathbf{p}_4 \dots \mathbf{p}_y) - 1 + \mathbf{\Pi}_{ns}(\mathbf{p}_y) \\ &= \mathbf{N}^{1/2} \times (1 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_1}/\mathbf{p}_1)(1 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_2}/\mathbf{p}_2)(1 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_3}/\mathbf{p}_3)(1 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_4}/\mathbf{p}_4) \dots (1 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_y}/\mathbf{p}_y) - 1 + \mathbf{\Pi}_{ns}(\mathbf{p}_y), \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{p}_y^2 \sim \mathbf{N}$, and $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_x}$, $\mathbf{x} = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, \mathbf{y}$, are the numbers of removed residue classes $(0 \bmod \mathbf{p}_x)$. The reason for adding $\mathbf{\Pi}_{ns}(\mathbf{p}_y)$ is because the primes smaller than or equal to \mathbf{p}_y are also removed by the sieve method,^[1,2] and “-1” is to remove number 1 when 1 is not considered as a prime number.

For a prime number $\mathbf{p} > 2$, $\mathbf{R}_p = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, \mathbf{p}-1\}$ is a set containing all the incongruent residues. Since $\mathbf{z}^2 \equiv (\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{z})^2 \pmod{\mathbf{p}}$ for any $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbf{R}_p$, $\mathbf{R}_{ns,p} = \{0^2+1, 1^2+1, 2^2+1, 3^2+1, \dots, (\mathbf{p}-1)^2+1\}$ has $(\mathbf{p}+1)/2$ incongruent residues modulo \mathbf{p} , and, except for $\mathbf{z} = 0$, there are exactly 2 elements, \mathbf{z} and $(\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{z})$, in \mathbf{R}_p such that $\mathbf{z}^2+1 \equiv (\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{z})^2+1 \pmod{\mathbf{p}}$ in $\mathbf{R}_{ns,p}$. If there exists a value $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbf{R}_p$ such that $\mathbf{z}^2+1 \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}}$, there also exists exactly another element, $(\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{z}) \in \mathbf{R}_p$, such that $(\mathbf{p}-\mathbf{z})^2+1 \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}}$. Thus, every $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_x}$, $\mathbf{x} = 2, 3, 4, \dots, \mathbf{y}$, in Eq. (1) is either 0 or 2. For $\mathbf{p}_1=2$, $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_1} = 1$. Thus, Eq. (2) becomes

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{ns}(\mathbf{N}) > \mathbf{N}^{1/2} \times (1-1/2)(1-2/3)(1-2/5)(1-2/7)(1-2/11) \dots (1-2/\mathbf{p}_y) - 1 + \mathbf{\Pi}_{ns}(\mathbf{p}_y) \quad (3)$$

Since $(1-1/2)(1-2/3)(1-2/5)(1-2/7)(1-2/11) \dots (1-2/\mathbf{p}_y) \sim 2\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{p}_y) \times [\ln(\mathbf{N})]^{-2}$,^[1,2] Eq. (3) becomes

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{ns}(\mathbf{N}) > 2\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{p}_y) \times \mathbf{N}^{1/2} / [\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{p}_y) = (1-1/2^2)(1-1/4^2)(1-1/6^2) \dots [1-1/(\mathbf{p}_y-1)^2]$ is the twin prime constant according to the first Hardy-Littlewood conjecture. $\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{p}_y) = \mathbf{C} \sim 0.660162$ when $\mathbf{p}_y \sim \mathbf{N}^{1/2}$ is very large.

Therefore, the conjecture of Landau's fourth problem that there are infinitely many near square primes of the form $\mathbf{n}^2 + 1$ has been affirmed since $\mathbf{N}^{1/2} / [\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2$ goes to infinity when \mathbf{N} is infinitely large.

III. Conclusion and Discussion

The conjecture of Landau's fourth problem that there are infinitely many near square primes of the form $\mathbf{n}^2 + 1$, has been affirmed. Again, it has been shown that sieve methods with indication of the Chinese remainder theorem are very powerful tools.

Though the analytical expression of Eq. (4) with mathematic approximation can prove that there are infinitely many near square primes of the form $\mathbf{n}^2 + 1$, Eq. (1) can also prove the same by showing there is at least one near square prime in between $\mathbf{n}^2 + 1$ and $(2\mathbf{n})^2 + 1$ for any large natural number \mathbf{n} , as follows:

Let $\mathbf{S}_n = \{\mathbf{b}^2 + 1 \mid \mathbf{b} \text{ is a natural number, and } \mathbf{n} < \mathbf{b} \leq 2\mathbf{n}\}$, and \mathbf{p}_y be the smallest prime that is greater than or equal to $[(2\mathbf{n})^2 + 1]^{1/2}$. The total number of elements in \mathbf{S}_n is \mathbf{n} . There are \mathbf{N}_r elements left after precluding the \mathbf{b} values that satisfy $\mathbf{b}^2 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}_x}$ for all $\mathbf{p}_x \leq \mathbf{p}_y \sim [(2\mathbf{n})^2 + 1]^{1/2}$. According to Eq. (1),

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{N}_r &\sim \mathbf{n} \times (\mathbf{p}_1 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_1})(\mathbf{p}_2 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_2})(\mathbf{p}_3 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_3})(\mathbf{p}_4 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_4}) \dots (\mathbf{p}_y - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_y}) / (\mathbf{p}_1 \mathbf{p}_2 \mathbf{p}_3 \mathbf{p}_4 \dots \mathbf{p}_y) \\ &= (\mathbf{p}_1 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_1}) [(\mathbf{p}_2 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_2}) / \mathbf{p}_1] [(\mathbf{p}_3 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_3}) / \mathbf{p}_2] [(\mathbf{p}_4 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_4}) / \mathbf{p}_3] \dots [(\mathbf{p}_x - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_x}) / \mathbf{p}_{x-1}] \dots [(\mathbf{p}_y - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_y}) / \mathbf{p}_{y-1}] (\mathbf{n} / \mathbf{p}_y) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

For $\mathbf{x} > 1$, $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_x}$ is equal to 0 or 2, and $[(\mathbf{p}_x - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_x}) / \mathbf{p}_{x-1}] \geq 1$.

For $\mathbf{x} = 1$, $\mathbf{p}_1 = 2$, $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_1} = 1$, and $(\mathbf{p}_1 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_1}) = 1$.

For $\mathbf{x} = 2$, $\mathbf{p}_2 = 3$, $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_2} = 0$, and $[(\mathbf{p}_2 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_2}) / \mathbf{p}_1] = [(3-0)/2] = 1.5$.

For $\mathbf{x} = 3$, $\mathbf{p}_3 = 5$, $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_3} = 2$, and $[(\mathbf{p}_3 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_3}) / \mathbf{p}_2] = [(5-2)/3] = 1$.

For $\mathbf{x} = 4$, $\mathbf{p}_4 = 7$, $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_4} = 0$, and $[(\mathbf{p}_4 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_4}) / \mathbf{p}_3] = [(7-0)/5] = 1.4$.

For $\mathbf{x} = 5$, $\mathbf{p}_5 = 11$, $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_5} = 0$, and $[(\mathbf{p}_5 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_5}) / \mathbf{p}_4] = [(11-0)/7] = 11/7$.

For $\mathbf{x} = 6$, $\mathbf{p}_6 = 13$, $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_6} = 2$, and $[(\mathbf{p}_6 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_6}) / \mathbf{p}_5] = [(11-2)/11] = 1$.

For $\mathbf{x} = 7$, $\mathbf{p}_7 = 17$, $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_7} = 2$, and $[(\mathbf{p}_7 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_7}) / \mathbf{p}_6] = [(17-2)/13] = 15/13$.

For $\mathbf{x} = 8$, $\mathbf{p}_8 = 19$, $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_8} = 0$, and $[(\mathbf{p}_8 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_8}) / \mathbf{p}_7] = [(19-0)/17] = 19/17$.

For $\mathbf{x} = 9$, $\mathbf{p}_9 = 23$, $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_9} = 0$, and $[(\mathbf{p}_9 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_9}) / \mathbf{p}_8] = [(23-0)/19] = 23/19$.

Thus, Eq. (5) becomes

$$\mathbf{N}_r \sim 5.15 \times [(\mathbf{p}_{10} - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_{10}}) / \mathbf{p}_{10}] \dots [(\mathbf{p}_x - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_x}) / \mathbf{p}_{x-1}] \dots [(\mathbf{p}_y - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_y}) / \mathbf{p}_{y-1}] (\mathbf{n} / \mathbf{p}_y) > 5.15 \times \mathbf{n} / \mathbf{p}_y \quad (6)$$

It is known that there is always a prime number between \mathbf{t} and $2\mathbf{t}$, where \mathbf{t} is a natural number. Thus, \mathbf{p}_y must be less than or equal to $2 \times [(2\mathbf{n})^2 + 1]^{1/2} \sim 4\mathbf{n}$, and Eq. (5) becomes

$$\mathbf{N}_r \sim > 5.15 \times \mathbf{n} / 4\mathbf{n} > 1. \quad (7)$$

Therefore, there is at least one element \mathbf{b} in \mathbf{S}_n such that $\mathbf{b}^2 + 1$ is prime and $\mathbf{n}^2 + 1 < \mathbf{b}^2 + 1 \leq (2\mathbf{n})^2 + 1$ for every large natural number \mathbf{n} . It is impossible for a maximum near square prime of the form $\mathbf{n}^2 + 1$ to exist.

The tools might be applicable to prove the existence of infinitely many primes of the form $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{n})$, which is a function of natural number \mathbf{n} , e.g. a polynomial, as long as $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{n})$ satisfies the following conditions:

1. $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{n})$ is always less than $\mathbf{n}^{\mathbf{m}}$, where \mathbf{m} is a constant natural number;
2. the maximum number of congruent residues in $\{\mathbf{F}(0), \mathbf{F}(1), \mathbf{F}(2), \mathbf{F}(3), \dots, \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{p}-1)\}$ is always less than a constant, \mathbf{k} , for all primes, $\mathbf{p} > \mathbf{k}$, and $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}} < \mathbf{p}$ for all $\mathbf{p} \leq \mathbf{k}$.

Let \mathbf{p}_a is the maximum prime that is less than or equal to \mathbf{k} in this case, then the prime counting function, $\mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{F}}(\mathbf{N})$ with $\mathbf{p}_y^2 \sim \mathbf{N}$, is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{F}}(\mathbf{N}) &\sim \mathbf{N}^{1/\mathbf{m}} \times (1 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_1}/\mathbf{p}_1)(1 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_2}/\mathbf{p}_2)(1 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_3}/\mathbf{p}_3) \dots (1 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_y}/\mathbf{p}_y) - 1 + \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{ns}}(\mathbf{p}_y) \\ &> \mathbf{N}^{1/\mathbf{m}} \times (1 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_1}/\mathbf{p}_1)(1 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_2}/\mathbf{p}_2)(1 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_3}/\mathbf{p}_3) \dots (1 - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{p}_a}/\mathbf{p}_a)(1 - \mathbf{k}/\mathbf{p}_{a+1}) \dots (1 - \mathbf{k}/\mathbf{p}_y) \\ &\sim \text{Constant} \times \mathbf{N}^{1/\mathbf{m}} / [\ln(\mathbf{N})]^{\mathbf{k}} \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

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V. Reference

1. Chern, G. C. (2025), "Sieves for Generating Prime k-tuples and Counting Functions", 10.5281/zenodo.18275704; 10.6084/m9.figshare.31080703.
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